

DETERMINATION OF FATTY ACID PROFILE AND EFFECT OF MIXOTROPHIC GROWTH IN SELECTED CYANOBACTERIAL STRAINS*

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SUMMARY: *Microalgae are photosynthetic microorganisms used in the nutrition of humans and animals (especially in aquaculture) due to the production of vitamins, proteins, polyunsaturated fatty acids, antioxidants, etc. Among microalgae, cyanobacteria (blue-green algae) are particularly recognized as the producers of different nutritive and biotechnologically valuable compounds. Although fatty acids of the microalgal origin are today available in the form of dietary supplements and are incorporated into various food products, microalgae are still an insufficiently explored source of these nutrients. In the present study, fatty acid compositions of four cyanobacterial strains belonging to the Nostoc and Anabaena genera have been analysed. Furthermore, since in photoautotrophic cultures, the biomass production of microalgae is mostly low, the present study reviews the effect of the mixotrophic mode of nutrition (besides CO₂ cells use organic matters as a carbon source) on the biomass production of the selected cyanobacteria.*

The analyses of fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) were carried out by gas chromatography coupled with flame ionization detection (GC-FID) after 42 days of the cyanobacterial cultivation. The results showed that the most significant constituents of these strains are 16 carbon (16:0 and 16:1 types) chain fatty acids, linoleic acid (18:2n6c) and α -linolenic acid (18:3n3). Oleic acid (18:1n9c) was also present in significant amounts, while myristic acid (14:0) and stearic acid (18:0) were present in small amounts. Erucic acid (22:1n9) was present in traces only in the strain Nostoc 2S₁, while caproic acid (6:0) and myristoleic acid (14:1) were present only in the strains Nostoc S₈ and Nostoc 2S₁.

For the purpose of determining the mixotrophic growth, the strains were cultured at different glucose concentrations (1.5 and 3 g/l) for 42 days, and the biomass

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production was determined periodically by spectrophotometrically measuring of the chlorophyll a concentration. The only strain which grew better in the autotrophic culture was *Anabaena* LC₁B, with the maximum production of only 0.1 g/l. In all the other strains, the biomass production of mixotrophic cultures surpassed 1g/l, at the lower concentration of glucose (1.5 g/l). The most productive strain was *Nostoc* 2S₃B, which, after 28 days with 1.43 g/l, had 18 times higher production in comparison with the autotrophic culture. The strains *Nostoc* S₈ and *Nostoc* 2S₁ were the most productive after 42 days, with 1.05 and 1.48 g/l, which was 1.32 and 4.84 times higher production than in the autotrophic cultures respectively.

Taking into account the aspects of biomass production in mixotrophic cultures with glucose and fatty acid composition, among the tested cyanobacterial strains, *Nostoc* 2S₃B has the greatest biotechnological potential.

Key words: *Cyanobacteria, fatty acids, mixotrophic growth*

INTRODUCTION

Microalgae are photosynthetic microorganisms with the vast potential in the production of food, feed and high-value metabolites. Although they have already been found as a source of number biologically active compounds such as carotenoids, phycobiliproteins, fatty acids, polysaccharides, vitamins and sterols (Singh et al., 2005; Thajuddin and Subramanian, 2005; Spolaore et al., 2006; Plaza et al., 2009), microalgae are proposed as almost unlimited source in search of novel natural functional ingredients (Plaza et al., 2009). Among microalgae, cyanobacteria (blue-green algae) are particularly recognized as health food, as well as producers of different bioactive compounds such as antiviral, anti-tumor, antibacterial, etc. (Singh et al., 2005).

Fatty acids of the microalgae origin are nowadays available in the form of dietary supplements, and incorporated into various food products. In each major algal group, fatty acids are generally recognized as characteristic of that group (Behrens and Kyle, 1996). The major saturated fatty acids within algae are 12, 14, 16 and 18 carbon fatty acids, while unsaturated fatty acids range from 16 to 22 carbons, containing from 1 to 6 double bonds in the cis-configuration (Behrens and Kyle, 1996). Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) play a key role in cellular and tissue metabolism (Cardozo et al., 2007). They are especially important as constituents of the membranes phospholipids, where they appear to confer distinctive properties, in particular by decreasing their rigidity. Among PUFAs ω -3 and ω -6 fatty acids belong to the essential fatty acids, and as they cannot be synthesized in human body, they have to be administered by diet. Algae are thought to be the principal producers of some PUFAs in the biosphere (Behrens and Kyle, 1996). Although marine fish is the principal dietary source of some PUFAs, they are actually synthesized by microalgae and fish receive them via food chain. In addition, using fish as a source is connected with problems such as pollutants accumulation, unpleasant odor, control of the fatty acids proportion, and also they are not suitable for vegetarians (Spolaore et al., 2006; Cannon, 2009). Moreover, since microalgae cells are rich in antioxidant carotenoids and vitamins, and lipids are bioencapsulated by the cell wall, microalgae may have superior lipid stability in comparison with traditional PUFAs (Patil et al., 2007). Among most important PUFAs, with numerous nutraceutical and pharmaceutical

applications are eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA, 20:5n3), docosahexaenoic acid (DHA, 22:6n3) and arachidonic acid (AA, 20:4n6). Different food products with incorporated oil of microalgae origin rich in these fatty acids, including formulations for infants, can be found on the market.

Today, microalgae are usually cultivated in photoautotrophic cultures and their commercial application is limited by the low biomass yield and high production costs. Using mixotrophic mode of nutrition biomass production, as well as target metabolites can be increased several times since organic matters are used as the second carbon and energy source. In mixotrophy within the cell, simultaneously occur photosynthesis and aerobic respiration, and during the night culture may continue to grow through heterotrophic nutrition. Moreover, production costs can be reduced because lower light intensity is required (Yu et al., 2009), cells can start to grow at a lower average light intensity (Yu et al., 2011) and there is less biomass loss during the dark phase (Andrade and Costa, 2007). It is showed that in some microalgae mixotrophy increased the level of lipids (Ceron Garcia et al., 2006; Wan et al., 2011; Kong et al., 2013), as well as fatty acids, such as EPA (Ceron Garcia et al., 2006). It is expected that mixotrophic cultivation is especially suitable for the production of high value bioactive compounds, fine chemicals and pharmaceuticals (Yu et al., 2011).

Filamentous, nitrogen-fixing cyanobacteria can be an excellent biotechnological source, because they do not need nitrogen in the culture medium, which results in reduction of production costs, while filamentous nature facilitates the process of biomass harvesting. Among them, some species of the *Anabaena* and *Nostoc* genera are used in human nutrition in Chile, Mexico, Peru and Philippines (Thajuddin and Subramanian, 2005). It is shown that *Anabaena sp.* PCC 7120 can be cultured for production of variety of fine chemicals and bioactive compounds, such as sulfolipids, pigments and exopolysaccharides, and it is very promising for production of high value transgenic proteins (cited in Yu et al., 2011). *Nostoc flagelliforme* is species with high economic value, used in nutrition for more than 2000 years, with reported anti-tumor and anti-viral activity (Yu et al., 2009). With high amount of fibre, species *Nostoc commune* is a potential dietary fibre source (Thajuddin and Subramanian, 2005).

The aim of this study was to investigate the fatty acid profile and effect of mixotrophic nutrition with glucose in selected filamentous, nitrogen-fixing cyanobacterial strains, belonging to the *Nostoc* and *Anabaena* genera.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the present study, four filamentous, nitrogen-fixing cyanobacterial strains were tested: *Anabaena* LC₁B, *Nostoc* S₈, *Nostoc* 2S₃B and *Nostoc* 2S₁. All strains were isolated from different soil types of Vojvodina region, then purified and cultured in BG-11 medium without nitrogen for 42 days, at room temperature.

Fatty acid methyl esters were prepared from the extracted lipids by transesterification using 14% boron (III)-fluoride in methanol (Karlović and Andrić, 1996). The obtained samples were analyzed by a GC Agilent 7890A system with flame-ionization detector (FID), autoinjection module for liquid samples, equipped with fused silica capillary column (DB-WAX 30 m, 0.25 mm, 0.50 µm). Helium was used as a carrier gas (purity > 99.9997 vol %, flow rate = 1.26 ml/min). The fatty acids peaks were identified by comparing retention times with retention times of

standards from Supelco 37 component fatty acid methyl ester mix (Sigma-Aldrich, EU) and with data from internal data library, which are based on previous experiments. Results were expressed as mass of fatty acid or fatty acid group (g) in 100 g of fatty acids.

Biomass production in mixotrophic conditions was determined at two concentrations of glucose (1.5 and 3 g/l). It was determined periodically, every seven days, by spectrophotometrically measuring of the chlorophyll a concentration, and it was calculated using an indirect method (Mckinney, 1941). Each sample was filtered (10 ml) and each filter paper was placed in a test tube in which was added 5 ml of methanol for extraction. This process lasted 24 hours in the dark at temperature 4°C. Samples were then sonicated 10 minutes in cycles of 30 seconds and centrifuged. Supernatants were collected and used for spectrophotometrical analysis of absorbance at 663 nm. The concentration of chlorophyll a was calculated using the following formula:

$$cc\ Chl\ a = \frac{A_{663} \times 12,64 \times V_1}{V_2} \left[\mu g / ml \right]$$

Where: ccChl a – chlorophyll a concentration [$\mu g/ml$]; A_{663} – absorbance at 663 nm; 12.64 – conversion factor; V_1 – sample volume [ml]; V_2 – methanol volume [ml]. Biomass production was calculated using the following formula:

$$B = ccChl\ a \times 67 \left[mg / ml \right]$$

Where 67 is conversion factor.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of fatty acid profile of tested cyanobacterial strains are shown in Table 1. The most significant constituents of tested cyanobacterial strains are 16 carbon (16:0 and 16:1 types) chain fatty acids, linoleic acid (18:2n6) and α -linolenic acid (18:3n3). Oleic acid (18:1n9) was also present in significant amounts, while myristic acid (14:0) and stearic acid (18:0) were present in small amounts. Erucic acid (22:1n9) was present in traces only in the strain *Nostoc* 2S₁, while caproic acid (6:0) and myristoleic acid (14:1) were present only in the strains *Nostoc* S₈ and *Nostoc* 2S₁. The results also showed that strain *Anabaena* LC₁B is the most suitable for production of 18:1n9c and 18:2n6c, strains *Nostoc* S₈ and *Nostoc* 2S₁ for 16:1, and strain *Nostoc* 2S₃B for 18:2n6c and 18:3n3. Finally, considering proportion of PUFAs in total fatty acids, strain *Nostoc* 2S₃B is the most promising.

In the present study, most significant constituents of tested strains are 16 carbon (16:0 and 16:1 types) chain fatty acids. It has been recently found that in animal tissues, palmitoleic acid (16:1n7) have a distinctive function in mice as a lipid hormone lipokine, while sapienic acid (16:1n10) is the single most abundant component in human sebum lipids. Among most significant fatty acids of tested strains are also linoleic acid (18:2n6) and α -linolenic acid (18:3n3), essential dietary components which in animal and plant tissues serve for synthesis of the remaining members of ω -6 and ω -3 family of fatty acids. Oleic acid (18:1n9) which was also

present in significant amounts, has number of important biological properties, and it is the biosynthetic precursor of a family of fatty acids with *n*-9 terminal structure and with chain lengths of 20 to 24, or more. Myristic acid (14:0), which is essential for the function of protein components in certain proteolipids was present in small amounts. This acid is a ubiquitous component of lipids in most living organisms, but usually at levels of only 1-2%. Milovanovic et al. (2012) investigated fatty acid profile in 3 filamentous, nitrogen-fixing cyanobacterial strains and as well as in our study, 16 carbon and 18 carbon chain fatty acids represented the most significant constituents, with the highest content of 16:1. Their strains as well had a significant amount of α -linolenic acid (18:3n3).

Table 1: Fatty acid profile of tested cyanobacterial strains

Fatty acid	<i>Anabaena</i> LC ₁ B	<i>Nostoc</i> S ₈	<i>Nostoc</i> 2S ₃ B	<i>Nostoc</i> 2S ₁
	%	%	%	%
6:0	0,00	20,75	0,00	2,21
14:0	0,54	0,66	0,66	0,68
14:1	0,00	0,49	0,00	0,47
16:0	21,57	12,23	15,94	18,29
16:1	26,45	31,63	24,83	36,75
18:0	0,80	0,47	3,11	0,70
18:1n9c	13,22	3,91	11,26	4,60
18:2n6c	19,59	16,00	20,09	15,64
18:3n3	17,82	13,85	24,10	20,13
22:1n9	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,53
SFA	22,90	34,11	19,72	21,88
MUFA	39,68	36,04	36,09	42,35
PUFA	37,42	29,86	44,19	35,77
UFA	77,10	65,89	80,28	78,12

SFA - saturated fatty acids, MUFA - monounsaturated fatty acids, PUFA - polyunsaturated fatty acids, UFA - unsaturated fatty acids

Furthermore, they also detected undecanoic acid (11:0), relatively rare γ -linoleic acid (GLA, 18:3n6), arachidic acid (20:0) and cis-13, 16-docosadienoic acid (22:2), which were not detected in our strains. Patil et al. (2007) tested fatty acid composition of 12 microalgae including two cyanobacterial strains, *Chroococcus* spp. and *Synechococcus* spp. *Chroococcus* spp. had 16:0 and 18:2n6 as the dominating fatty acids, with lower amounts of 16:1 and 18:3n3, while in *Synechococcus* spp. the most abundant were 14:0, 16:0 and 16:1. Viso and Marty (1993) reported the fatty acid composition of 28 marine microalgae species. Among tested cyanobacteria, *Anacystis quadruplicatum* was characterized by a high proportion of PUFA 18:3n3 and 16:2n6,

while *A. marina* and *Synechocystis* sp. were rich in monounsaturated 16:1n9. In the study of Milovanovic et al. (2012), among tested cyanobacterial strains *Spirulina*, strains had the highest content of GLA (18:3n6) and significant amount of cis-11-eicosenoic acid (20:1). Interestingly, species *Spirulina platensis* represents a source of many fatty acids which are potential functional ingredients, i.e. oleic acid (antioxidant activity), linolenic acid (antimicrobial activity), and palmitoleic acid and DHA (reduce risk of certain heart diseases) (cited in Plaza et al., 2009). In this species, DHA (22:6n3) can account up to 9.1% of the total fatty acids content (Yukino et al., 2005). The study of Patil et al. (2007) revealed that in all the tested 12 microalgae, major saturated fatty acid was 16:0, while major monosaturated fatty acids were 16:1 or 18:1. According to them, marine algae are major producers of the ω 3-PUFAs (EPA and DHA), while in the freshwater algae dominate saturated or monosaturated fatty acids. In cyanobacteria major fatty acids are 16:0 and 16:1 (Behrens and Kyle, 1996). Furthermore, the fatty acid compositions (particularly their content of monounsaturated and PUFAs) shown to be different for unicellular and filamentous algae (Kenyon and Stanier, 1970). In addition, while some algae produce large quantities of lipids in form of large droplets of triacylglycerol in the cytoplasm (Boswell et al., 1992), cyanobacteria generally do not produce oils as a storage material, and virtually all fatty acids are present as complex lipids used for cells photosynthetic membrane system (Behrens and Kyle, 1996).

The results of biomass production in mixotrophic cultures are presented in Graph. 1-4. The only strain which grew better in autotrophic culture was *Anabaena* LC₁B, with maximum production of only 0.1 g/l. In all other strains, biomass production of mixotrophic cultures surpassed 1g/l, at the lower concentration of glucose (1.5 g/l). The most productive strain was *Nostoc* 2S₃B, which, after 28 days with 1.43 g/l, had 18 times higher production in comparison with autotrophic culture. Strains *Nostoc* S₈ and *Nostoc* 2S₁ were most productive after 42 days, with 1.32 and 4.84 times higher production than in autotrophic cultures respectively. Furthermore, strains *Nostoc* S₈ and *Nostoc* 2S₃B were more productive at 1.5 g/l of glucose, in relation to *Nostoc* 2S₁ which showed higher biomass production at 3 g/l of glucose. Gradual increase of biomass during time in strains *Nostoc* S₈ and *Nostoc* 2S₁ could indicate adaptation of strains to mixotrophic mode of nutrition, since in laboratory they have been routinely maintained in phototrophic cultures. The most productive strain *Nostoc* 2S₃B in mixotrophic cultures showed decrease of biomass, due the exhaustion of glucose.

Graph. 1. Biomass production in strain *Anabaena* LC₁B

Graph. 2. Biomass production in strain *Nostoc S8*

Graph. 3. Biomass production in strain *Nostoc 2S1*

Graph. 4. Biomass production in strain *Nostoc 2S3B*

There are many studies which showed that mixotrophic cultivation can significantly increase biomass production. In *Nostoc flagelliforme* biomass production in mixotrophic culture was 4.98 times higher than in autotrophic culture (Yu et al., 2009). In the study of Bhatnagar et al. (2011), mixotrophic growth of 3 microalgae was 3-10 times higher relative to phototrophic growth. It is considered that under mixotrophic conditions exist synergistic effects of heterotrophy and phototrophy (Bhatnagar et al., 2011). As the final metabolite of respiratory metabolism, CO₂ can be recycled for photoautotrophic growth (Cheirsilp and Torpee, 2012). In mixotrophic culture of *Anabaena* PCC 7120, increased activities of glucokinase and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase indicated ability of cellular metabolism regulation of exogenous glucose at least at enzymatic levels (Yu et al., 2011). However, the degree

of utilization of different carbon sources is species specific phenomenon affected by the presence of specific permeases (Bhatnagar et al., 2011).

CONCLUSION

Cyanobacteria are microorganisms with enormous biotechnological potential. It is expected that their commercial application will grow with the development of technology and that will increase biomass production and decrease production costs. Therefore mixotrophic cultivation can be considered as very promising. Cyanobacteria are certainly important source of fatty acids. Strains which were tested in the present study showed ability to produce important fatty acids, as well as significant biomass increase in mixotrophic cultivation conditions. Taking into account the highest content of polyunsaturated fatty acids, as well as the highest biomass production, strain *Nostoc* 2S₃B has the greatest biotechnological potential.

REFERENCES

- ANDRADE, M.R., COSTA, J.A.V.: Mixotrophic cultivation of microalga *Spirulina platensis* using molasses as organic substrate. *Aquaculture*, 264(1-4)130–134, 2007.
- BEHRENS, P., KYLE, D.: Microalgae as a source of fatty acids. *Journal of food lipids*, 3(4)259-272, 1996.
- BHATNAGAR, A., CHINNASAMY, S., SINGH, M., DAS, K.C.: Renewable biomass production by mixotrophic algae in the presence of various carbon sources and wastewaters. *Applied Energy*. 88(10)3425–3431, 2011.
- BOSWELL, K.D.B., GLADUE, R., PRIMA, B., KYLE, D.J. 1992. SCO Production by Fermentative Microalgae. In: *Industrial Applications of Single Cell Oils*. (D.J. Kyle and C. Ratledge. eds.) pp. 274-286. American Oil Chemists' Society, Champaign, IL.
- CARDOZO, K.H.M., GUARATINI, T., BARROS, M.P., FALCÃO, V.R., TONON, A.P., LOPES, N.P., CAMPOS, S., TORRES, M.A., SOUZA, A.O., COLEPICOLO, P., PINTO, E.: Metabolites from algae with economical impact. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology*, Part C, 146(1-2)60–78, 2007.
- CANNON, D.: From fish oil to microalgae oil... a win-win shift for humans and our habitat. *Explore*, 5(5)299-303, 2009.
- CERÓN GARCÍA, M.C., GARCÍA CAMACHO, F., SÁNCHEZ MIRÓN, A., FERNÁNDEZ SEVILLA, J.M., CHISTI, Y., MOLINA GRIMA, E.: Mixotrophic production of marine microalga *Phaeodactylum tricoratum* on various carbon sources. *J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 16(5)689–694, 2006.
- CHEIRSILP, B., TORPEE, S.: Enhanced growth and lipid production of microalgae under mixotrophic culture condition: Effect of light intensity, glucose concentration and fed-batch cultivation. *Bioresource Technology*, 110, 510–516, 2012.
- CHEN, F., ZHANG, Y.: High cell density mixotrophic culture of *Spimlina platensis* on glucose for phycocyanin production using a fed-batch system. *Enzyme and Microbial Technology*, 20, 221-224, 1997.
- KARLOVIĆ, Đ., ANDRIĆ, N. (1996). Kontrola kvaliteta semena uljarica, Univerzitet u Novom Sadu, Tehnološki fakultet Novi Sad, Savezno ministarstvo za nauku tehnologiju i razvoj, Savezni zavod za standardizaciju, Beograd.
- KENYON, C.N., STANIER, R.Y.: Possible evolutionary significance of polyunsaturated fatty acids in blue-green algae. *Nature*, 1970. Cited in Viso and Marty, 1993.
- KONG, W.B., YANG, H., CAO, Y.T., SONG, H., HUA, S.F., XIA, C.G.: Effect of glycerol and glucose on the enhancement of biomass, lipid and soluble carbohydrate production by *Chlorella vulgaris* in mixotrophic culture. *Food Technol. Biotechnol.* 51(1)62–69, 2013.

- MCKINNEY, G.: Absorption of light by chlorophyll solutions. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 140, 315–322, 1941.
- MILOVANOVIĆ, I., MIŠAN, A., ŠARIĆ, B., KOS, J., MANDIĆ, A., SIMEUNOVIĆ, J., KOVAČ, D.: Evaluation of protein and lipid content and determination of fatty acid profile in selected species of cyanobacteria. *Proceedings of 6th Central European Congress on Food*, Novi Sad, Serbia, 23-26 May, 2012. pp. 13-17.
- PATIL, V., KALLQVIST, T., OLSEN, E., VOGT, G., GISLEROD, H.: Fatty acid composition of 12 microalgae for possible use in aquaculture feed. *Aquacult. Int.*, 15(1)1–9, 2007.
- PLAZA, M., HERRERO, M., CIFUENTES, A., IBANEZ, E.: Innovative natural functional ingredients from microalgae. *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 57(16)7159–7170, 2009.
- SINGH, S., KATE, B.N., BANERJEE, U.C.: Bioactive compounds from cyanobacteria and microalgae: An Overview. *Critical Reviews in Biotechnology*, 25(3)73-95, 2005.
- SPOLAORE, P., JOANNIS-CASSAN, C., DURAN, E., ISAMBERT, A.: Commercial applications of microalgae. *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*, 101(2)87–96, 2006.
- THAJUDDIN, N., SUBRAMANIAN, G.: Cyanobacterial biodiversity and potential applications in biotechnology. *Current Science*, 89(1)47-57, 2005.
- VISO, A., MARTY, J.: Fatty acids from 28 marine microalgae. *Phytochemistry*, 34(6)1521-1533, 1993.
- WAN, M., LIU, P., XIA, J., ROSENBERG, J.N., OYLER, G.A., BETENBAUGH, M.J., NIE, Z., QIU, G.: The effect of mixotrophy on microalgal growth, lipid content, and expression levels of three pathway genes in *Chlorella sorokiniana*. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol*, 91(3)835–844, 2011.
- YU, G., SHI, D., CAI, Z., CONG, W., OUYANG, F.: Growth and physiological features of cyanobacterium *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 in a glucose-mixotrophic culture. *Chinese Journal of Chemical Engineering*, 19(1)108-115, 2011.
- YU, H., SHIRU, J., YUJIE, D.: Growth characteristics of the cyanobacterium *Nostoc flagelliforme* in photoautotrophic, mixotrophic and heterotrophic cultivation. *J. Appl. Phycol.*, 21(1)127–133, 2009.
- YUKINO, T., HAYASHI, M., INOUE, Y., IMAMURA, J., NAGANO, N., MURATA, H.: Preparation of docosahexaenoic acid fortified *Spirulina platensis* and its lipid and fatty acid compositions. *Nippon Suisan Gakk.*, 71, 74–79, 2005.